
Application of Accounting Principles to Improve the Quality of Fund Management at Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati Elementary School

Muhammad Alif Nuril ‘Ibad¹, Ainas Sa’adah², Abdul Wahid³

^{1,2,3}Postgraduate in Islamic Education Management, Walisongo State Islamic University, Semarang, 50151

ABSTRACT

Improving the quality of fund management is essential in educational institutions, especially to meet and ensure students' needs for quality learning. Therefore, MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Margoyoso Pati optimizes its fund management system by applying accounting principles. This study aims to identify in depth the application of accounting principles to improve the quality of educational fund management at MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Margoyoso Pati effectively and efficiently. This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. The results of this study indicate that MI Mambaul Huda has significant government funding for operations and encourages highly accountable and transparent accounting practices. The optimization of educational fund management must be classified in detail to measure the cost efficiency per unit or per student and ensure that the budget allocation truly supports quality improvement and meets the learning process needs of students at the madrasah. The principles of educational accounting are applied to facilitate the fund management process, including the principles of historical cost accounting, revenue recognition, matching, consistency, and full/complete disclosure, so that financial reports can serve as parameters in quality control and evaluation based on an approach of fund management efficiency to achieve educational goals.

KEYWORDS: Educational Accounting, Fund Management.

ARTICLE DETAILS

**Published On:
26 February 2026**

**Available on:
<https://ijiiissh.com/>**

A. INTRODUCTION

Islamic educational institutions are strategic and complex entities in carrying out their role of providing education, especially Islamic religious education, one of which is madrasahs. The education system in madrasahs operates to meet learning needs while adjusting to established educational standards. In the process of meeting the needs of madrasahs, it is necessary to manage finances and ensure fair and equitable access to education for all students (Amaliyah & Giu, 2023). The dynamics of developments in the education sector require madrasahs to operate efficiently and have adequate resources.

Basically, madrasahs need to manage education financing effectively, such as allocating resources appropriately and planning costs that take into account the welfare of educators and operational needs, thereby helping madrasahs to achieve quality education (Solehan, 2022). Using the concept of financing or financial management makes it easier for educational institutions to achieve quality standards (Andawiyah, 2025). Efforts to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of educational financing in madrasahs are key factors in determining the quality of educational outcomes and shaping the sustainability of the education system. Therefore, improving the quality of madrasahs involves managing and optimizing educational financing.

Suboptimal management of education funds in schools and madrasahs significantly causes a decline in the quality of education and reduces the effectiveness of madrasahs or schools. Research by Nurhidayatullah et al. found that schools with sufficient financial resources often use most of these funds for financing without proper planning, implementation, or evaluation, thereby limiting the development and improvement of teaching quality in schools (Nurhidayatullah & Aimah, 2025). Meanwhile, in another study, educational institutions face challenges in implementing financial management in schools, including inadequate funding, poor financial planning, and insufficient management capacity (Musa, 2021). There are key issues in education financial management that center on three important components, namely planning, accounting, and auditing systems, which need to be addressed appropriately and more effectively. The concern is that even when adequate educational funds are available, poor management practices prevent quality improvement. Therefore, optimizing school financial management effectively requires not only sufficient

Application of Accounting Principles to Improve the Quality of Fund Management at Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati Elementary School

funding but also a better planning, implementation, and evaluation system, as well as competent and ethical human resources to oversee financial operations (Zumarti, Amran, Mudasir, & Syarif, 2022).

Optimizing madrasah financial management involves three main cycles: budgeting, accounting, and auditing, which are interrelated and must be implemented in a transparent, accountable, and efficiency-oriented manner. In practice, madrasahs face several challenges, such as weak accounting and reporting systems, a lack of managerial competence among administrators, and limited financial resources, which have implications for the sustainability of educational programs (Rahayu & Lemmy, 2024). In response to these issues, this study emphasizes the importance of optimizing the education fund management system, particularly in the processes of budget planning, financing or accounting implementation, and education fund reporting in schools.

An important part of the financial management of an educational institution is educational accounting, which is directly related to how well educational financing functions and reflects the effectiveness of the financial resources available at the school. Educational institutions use accounting as a means of summarizing, recording, and reporting transactions that occur within a certain period of time (Veronika & Asriati, 2024). According to Indra Bastian, educational accounting is the process of managing, recording, classifying, summarizing, and reporting financial resources in an educational institution (Indra Bastian, 2006). All forms of operational activities of an educational institution are inseparable from the financial side so that they can be known through accounting information presented systematically in the form of financial reports, becoming a tangible form or evidence of the entire state of the organization, including the efforts or performance and development of educational institutions (Enny Kartini, 2024).

Accounting practices applied in a company or institution must comply with generally accepted accounting principles. The application of generally accepted accounting principles will result in financial statements that are relevant and easy to understand by various parties who need such information, including fund management in Islamic educational institutions. There are five principles in accounting for education in schools or madrasahs. First, the historical cost principle requires school assets to be reported based on their acquisition price or recorded based on their purchase price, not their market value, in order to maintain objectivity. Second, the revenue recognition principle is applied when schools recognize funds (such as tuition fees or BOS funds) when the right to receive them has occurred or services have been provided, not when the funds are received. Third, the matching principle is a principle that ensures that matching costs with the income generated is useful for determining the amount of net income for each period. Fourth, the consistency principle requires schools to use the same accounting methods from year to year to facilitate performance comparison and evaluation. Finally, the full disclosure principle requires schools to present all material financial information, including important notes on restricted funds from donors, to meet public accountability requirements (Ristiyani, Solichatun, & Dimiyati, 2023).

Based on research conducted at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Mambaul Huda in Tunjungrejo village, Margoyoso subdistrict, Pati district, from a documentation study of financial reports on the implementation of accounting or recording of transactions using funds to finance all learning and madrasah development needs, there are still inefficiencies in the technical aspects of financing management, such as in the 2025 RKAM (madrasah activity and budget plan) report of MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati, which shows structural deficiencies in educational fund accounting, indicating that the quality of educational fund management at MI Mambaul Huda is still relatively low. In reality, the accounting process has summarized all forms of transactions, but the report has not classified expenditures in detail, such as the separation of quality program costs and administrative costs. The limitations in calculating the unit cost or costs incurred per student in accordance with the learning needs of students at the madrasah have not been explicitly recorded. In this aspect, it is not possible to show the amount of education costs per student (unit cost) properly, because the unlisted unit cost makes it difficult to evaluate the report as accountability to the foundation and donors or the community. As a result, the financial reports at MI Mambaul Huda cannot be used as material for analysis in determining the quality of education at the madrasah in accordance with accounting principles and the transparency and accountability that apply in the management of education funds.

Therefore, based on the financial statements, it is evident that the costs incurred indicate an inefficient allocation of funds that is not yet strategic and does not utilize cost-benefit analysis in the allocation of madrasah funds, resulting in suboptimal management of educational funds at MI Mambaul Huda. From reviewing these issues, it can be understood that the best accounting practices or implementation at MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati are not only an administrative function but also a strategic management tool that supports optimal financing management. In addition, there are ideal demands related to the reality of educational fund management practices, which are still simple and not yet fully based on accounting principles in accordance with standards. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring how the application of accounting principles and optimization of financing management has failed because the principal does not have accurate data to make evidence-based decisions.

Referring to the above issues, this study aims to identify in depth the application of accounting principles to improve the quality of education fund management at MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Margoyoso Pati effectively and efficiently. This research is important from an academic perspective to fill the literature gap regarding the efficiency of education financing in schools or

Application of Accounting Principles to Improve the Quality of Fund Management at Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati Elementary School

madrasahs and to achieve quality education. In addition, the results of this study are expected to be a reference source that can be used by other schools for the optimal, effective, and efficient empowerment and management of financial resources.

B. METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. The qualitative approach with the case study method is based on the problem of education fund management at MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati, which aims to identify the application of accounting principles in the practice of education fund management in madrasahs, in order to achieve efficiency and effectiveness in the allocation of madrasah financial resources as a form of quality improvement in the education and learning process at MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati. Qualitative research is a research approach used to explore and understand the meanings held by individuals or groups, with the aim of describing certain conditions, phenomena, issues, or events in depth. Meanwhile, a case study is a type of qualitative research conducted in certain circumstances in depth and comprehensively using programs, activities, events, and groups (Agung Widhi Kurniawan & Puspitaningtyas, 2023).

This research was conducted at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati. This madrasah is located on Jalan Raya Tayu-Juwana KM 06, Tunjungrejo Village, Margoyoso District, Pati Regency. The data collection techniques used in this study were interviews, observation, and documentation study. Interviews are a data collection method conducted through verbal conversation, either face-to-face with informants or through other media without physical meetings. Meanwhile, observation is the activity of focusing attention on an object using all the senses. In addition, documentation studies involve searching for data on matters or variables in the form of notes, transcripts, books, newspapers, magazines, inscriptions, meeting minutes, agendas, and so on (Arikunto, 2010). The researcher conducted interviews with the principal and treasurer of MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati. In addition to interviews, the researcher also conducted observations, namely observing the treasurer while performing recording or transaction tasks in journals or financial books. In the documentation study, the researcher reviewed and analyzed documents related to education funds at the madrasah, such as the RKAM (madrasah activity and budget plan). After the data was collected, the next stage was to analyze the data from the research data collection results.

Data analysis was conducted systematically from the results of data collection from interviews, observations, and documentation. Lexy J. Moleong explains that the data obtained in the research may come from interviews, field notes, photographs, personal documents, and official documents, which are analyzed by organizing the data, breaking it down into units, synthesizing the data, compiling and selecting what is important, and making conclusions that can be communicated to others as research findings (Lexy J. Moeleong, 2013). The descriptive analytical data analysis technique is a method used for data that has been collected after data collection, then compiled, explained, and analyzed. Because the data collected is qualitative data, the method used to analyze the data is descriptive analysis. Descriptive analysis techniques analyze data not in the form of numbers, but in the form of reports and descriptive explanations using inductive thinking, which is a way of thinking from specific facts and concrete events, then generalized into concepts or conclusions that form general data results (Sugiyono, 2013). This method is used to analyze specific data that has similarities so that it becomes a conclusion and is used to analyze research data related to the application of accounting principles in improving the quality of fund management at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Tunjungrejo Pati.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research through interviews and documentation studies, it shows that the main source of funding for MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati comes from BOS funds. In addition, other sources of funding at MI Mambaul Huda include funds from waqaf and voluntary assistance from the community. The allocation of BOS funds at MI Mambaul Huda is channeled for learning needs at the madrasah, so that students at MI Mambaul Huda are exempt from registration fees, monthly tuition fees, and administration fees. All students are provided with school supplies, including uniforms, stationery, shoes, and textbooks, free of charge. All of these are provided by the madrasah for the students.

No.	Sumber Dana	Total Anggaran
1.	APBN BOS Triwulan 1	Rp. 46.060.000
2.	APBN BOS Triwulan 2	Rp. 46.060.000
3.	APBN BOS Triwulan 3 & 4	Rp. 92.120.000
	Total	Rp. 184.240.000

Based on the above data obtained from documentary studies, the 2025 BOS funds at MI Mambaul Huda show that the total annual BOS fund allocation reaches IDR 184,240,000, with a proportional distribution where each quarter 1 and 2 receive IDR 46,060,000 and quarters 3 and 4 receive a double allocation of IDR 92,120,000 (IDR 46,060,000 x 2). If each student receives assistance from the BOS fund in the amount of Rp. 1,047,000 with a total of 176 students, the figure of Rp. 1,047,000 is rounded or estimated from

Application of Accounting Principles to Improve the Quality of Fund Management at Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati Elementary School

the standard figure used by the government to be slightly lower at around Rp. 1,046,818 per student, bringing the total to Rp. 184,240,000. This data shows that MI Mambaul Huda has significant government funding for operations, as well as encouraging highly accountable and transparent accounting practices. The optimization of education fund management must be classified in detail to measure the cost efficiency per unit or per student and ensure that the budget allocation truly supports quality improvement and meets the learning needs of students at the madrasah.

Financing at MI Mambaul Huda

Financing at MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati is coordinated and implemented with a financial management structure divided into three treasurers, namely the foundation treasurer, the BOS treasurer, and the madrasah treasurer. The foundation treasurer holds and manages the finances received from the foundation. If the madrasah needs financial assistance, the foundation will provide funding sources, such as when constructing a new building. In addition, the foundation treasurer also manages funds generated from waqaf, which is a fixed income for the madrasah, such as the leasing of fish ponds, which provides the madrasah with additional financial resources, even though the amount generated is still less than other funding sources. In strengthening the school's funding sources, the foundation and the madrasah board of directors also contribute greatly to attracting donors, thereby fulfilling needs such as learning facilities at MI MHT in order to achieve quality education. In the research by Arif Fiandi and Junaidi, it was shown that foundations can collect and use their funds according to the needs of developing the educational institutions they manage (Fiandi & Junaidi, 2022). Thus, foundations function as management bodies responsible for the operational continuity of schools, as well as playing a role in asset management, fundraising, and supervision of school management.

The BOS treasurer is responsible for managing and assisting the head of the madrasah in carrying out BOS treasury functions at the educational unit (Direktur Jendral Pendidikan Islam, 2024). The BOS treasurer serves as the main manager responsible for the smooth and sustainable management of education funds related to BOS funds and carries out financing management tasks at the madrasah. BOS funds are allocated and supervised through a structured mechanism in accordance with government regulations, whereby the BOS treasurer is responsible for managing government education assistance funds to support madrasah operations in providing quality education and learning at the madrasah.

From the data in the 2025 First Quarter BOS fund document at MI Mambaul Huda, funds are allocated evenly between program quality needs, with a percentage of 50.15% of the BOS funds amounting to Rp 23,100,000, and operational/administrative needs, with a percentage of 49.85% or Rp 22,960,000. This allocation demonstrates a commitment to improving the quality of learning facilities at MI Mambaul Huda with a focus on educational quality. However, the high proportion of the operational budget detailed in best accounting practices explicitly separates the unit cost of learning programs from general administrative costs.

The important aspects applied and inherent in MI Mambaul Huda in managing educational funds are based on a culture of sincerity, consistency, and Islamic charitable values. For example, certified teachers contribute Rp 250,000 from their monthly government salaries as charity, thereby helping to finance the welfare of the madrasah community. In addition, there is assistance in the construction of the madrasah from the charitable deeds of the community, parents, and alumni, which shows a high level of social concern for the madrasah, due to the trust and sincerity of the teachers at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati. This phenomenon reflects the excellence of the madrasah, where teachers not only carry out amal ilmi (teaching) but also amal maddiyah (voluntary financial contributions) to support education and learning programs at the madrasah. The management practices and culture of the madrasah scientifically optimize resource allocation at a lower cost, resulting in educational funding efficiency, while also demonstrating the madrasah's commitment to educating students with a focus on achieving sustainable learning quality.

The important aspects applied and inherent in MI Mambaul Huda in managing educational funds are based on a culture of sincerity, consistency, and Islamic charitable values. For example, certified teachers contribute Rp 250,000 from their monthly government salaries as charity, thereby helping to finance the welfare of the madrasah community. In addition, there is assistance in the construction of the madrasah from the charitable deeds of the community, parents, and alumni, which shows a high level of social concern for the madrasah, due to the trust and sincerity of the teachers at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati. This phenomenon reflects the excellence of the madrasah, where teachers not only impart knowledge (teaching) but also make voluntary financial contributions to support education and learning programs at the madrasah. The management practices and culture of the madrasah scientifically optimize resource allocation at a lower cost, resulting in educational funding efficiency, while also demonstrating the madrasah's commitment to educating students with a focus on achieving sustainable learning quality.

Quality of Education Fund Management Through Accounting Principles at MI Mambaul Huda

Education funds are managed through accounting stages at MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati, particularly in the receipt and expenditure of BOS funds, which involves a structured process starting from planning to the preparation of the RKAM, which is used as the basis for financing education at the madrasah. The management of BOS funds aims to allocate and use funds

Application of Accounting Principles to Improve the Quality of Fund Management at Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati Elementary School

appropriately and direct activities to be carried out so that they do not deviate from the predetermined direction. It should be noted that in managing the BOS fund budget, among other things, the analysis of cash receipts and expenditures must be in with the budget that has been made (Pebrianto, Stie, & Balikpapan, 2022). Therefore, the process that is taken into account in BOS fund accounting is to analyze transactions or receipts and expenditures must be in accordance with accounting principles in optimizing the management of madrasah financing and supporting the sustainability and improvement of education quality at MI Mambaul Huda. Based on an interview with the treasurer of BOS MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati, he said that the concept and method of accounting for financing at MI Mambaul Huda are carried out based on the principles of financing management. The financial recording process at the madrasah must include budget planning, realization, and clear accountability to related parties. The implementation of accounting at MI Mambaul Huda begins with the collection of transaction evidence, recording each transaction that occurs in a journal, and then summarizing it into financial reports in an accountable and transparent manner. The fund receipt system at MI Mambaul Huda involves managing a number of financial sources that come into the madrasah, which are used to finance all operational and development activities that have been planned in the madrasah's activity plan and budget. Meanwhile, expenditures are funds disbursed by the madrasah to implement programs that have been outlined in the madrasah's work plan and budget (RKAM).

Based on an interview with the principal of MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati, financial reports must always be prepared in accordance with the budget plan that has been made. The preparation of financial reports must always be guided by the budget plan that has been made, so that it reflects the principles of accounting practice, where financial reports not only serve as historical records, but also serve to ensure the optimization and efficiency of educational fund management for madrasah operations.

The accounting process involves collecting and processing financial data to be presented in the form of financial reports or other summaries related to budget or financial records that can be used to assist in making or taking decisions (Indra Bastian, 2006). Best accounting practices have a significant positive impact on the quality of education fund management in schools. Several studies show that, as in the study by N. Nyanyuki et al., 2013, accounting practices explain 92.1% of the variation in fund management, with a significant correlation based on statistical analysis (Nyanyuki, Nyabwanga, & Nyamwamu, 2013). Meanwhile, Grace Ndinda Kimuyu et al., 2021, emphasized that budgeting, recording, bookkeeping, and internal control related to school finances have a significant effect on fund management (Kimuyu, Naibei, & Sang, 2021). Educational accounting principles ensure the accountability and objectivity of school financial reporting, thereby facilitating the fund management process. The accounting principles consist of the historical cost principle, the revenue recognition principle, the matching principle, the consistency principle, and the full disclosure principle (Ristiyani et al., 2023).

The application of accounting principles in improving quality and assisting the effectiveness of fund management at MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati, based on interviews and analysis of financial data related to RKAM, shows that the accounting practice applied by the madrasah on the historical cost principle requires the madrasah to record fixed assets and investment assets in the madrasah's financial statements at the acquisition price at the time of the transaction. Funds are received with reference to the revenue recognition principle, which distinguishes between restricted and unrestricted funds, and the matching principle, which matches costs with revenues, such as the budget from the madrasah's funds and the madrasah's spending or operational needs. The consistency principle requires madrasahs to use the same method so that financial statements can be compared because they have the same recording system. Improvements in fund management can be seen from the refinement of the recording system, which allows for detailed classification to meet the full disclosure principle and facilitates the calculation of unit costs. By presenting transparent reports, the credibility of madrasah financial reports will increase, enabling madrasah principals to provide analysis for consideration in decision-making to achieve quality learning programs at MI Mambaul Huda. Therefore, the BOS treasurer, madrasah treasurer, and foundation treasurer must manage finances in accordance with accounting principles so that financial reports can serve as a tool for accountability and quality measurement for the achievement of educational goals.

D. CONCLUSION

The optimization of education fund management must be classified in detail to measure cost efficiency, so that the allocation of education funds truly supports quality improvement and meets the learning needs of students. The practice of fund management in madrasahs and the madrasah culture applied at MI Mambaul Huda in managing education funds is based on a culture of sincerity, consistency, and Islamic charitable values, scientifically optimizing resource allocation at a lower cost, resulting in efficiency in education financing, while also becoming the madrasah's commitment to educating students oriented towards obtaining sustainable learning quality. The principles of educational accounting are applied to help facilitate the fund management process. The BOS treasurer, madrasah treasurer, and foundation treasurer must manage finances in recording transactions or the process of income and expenditure in accordance with accounting principles, namely the historical cost principle, revenue recognition principle, matching

Application of Accounting Principles to Improve the Quality of Fund Management at Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati Elementary School

principle, consistency principle, and full disclosure principle, so that financial reports can serve as parameters in quality control and evaluation based on an approach of efficient management and utilization of funds to achieve educational goals.

E. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers would like to thank the lecturers of the educational financing management course for teaching useful knowledge and providing input for the research and master's program in Islamic Education Management at Walisongo State Islamic University Semarang for the opportunity to innovate academically and for the resources provided during this research process. Thanks are also extended to MI Mambaul Huda Tunjungrejo Pati for permitting this research to be conducted and assisting in providing research data so that this research could be completed successfully.

REFERENCES

- 1) Agung Widhi Kurniawan, & Puspitaningtyas, Z. (2023). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif (Edisi Revisi)*. Medan: Yayasan Kita Menulis.
- 2) Amaliyah, K., & Giu, I. Y. (2023). Manajemen Pembiayaan Pendidikan yang Efektif di Madrasah Tsanawiyah Swasta. *Epistemic: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*, 2(1), 20–35. <https://doi.org/10.70287/EPITEMIC.V2I1.107>
- 3) Andawiyah, R. (2025). *AL-AFKAR : Journal for Islamic Studies Manajemen Pembiayaan Dalam Meningkatkan Mutu Lembaga Pendidikan Islam*. 8(2), 1086–1096. <https://doi.org/10.31943/afkarjournal.v8i2.1436.Financing>
- 4) Arikunto, S. (2010). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta.
- 5) Direktur Jendral Pendidikan Islam. (2024). *Juknis BOS dan BOP TH 2024*.
- 6) Enny Kartini. (2024). Konsep Akuntansi Pendidikan dalam Pengelolaan Perguruan Tinggi. *Kinabalu*, 11(2), 50–57.
- 7) Fiandi, A., & Junaidi. (2022). Sumber-Sumber Dana Pendidikan. *JURNAL BASICEDU*, 6(6), 10414–10421. <https://doi.org/DOI> : <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v6i6.4391>
- 8) Indra Bastian. (2006). *Akuntansi Pendidikan*. Semarang: Erlangga. Retrieved from https://books.google.co.id/books?id=uW9K2kD7Sm4C&printsec=copyright&hl=id&source=gbs_pub_info_r#v=onepage&q&f=false
- 9) Kimuyu, G. N., Naibei, I., & Sang, H. (2021). *Relationship Between Accounting Practices and Management of Funds In Public Secondary Schools in Kisii County, Kenya*.
- 10) Lexy J. Moeleong. (2013). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 11) Musa, F. (2021). Aspek-Aspek Finansial Pendidikan Islam. *Edu Religia Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Dan Keagamaan*, 5(2). Retrieved from <http://jurnal.uinsu.ac.id/index.php/eduriligia/index>
- 12) Nurhidayatullah, & Aimah, S. (2025). Education Financing Management in Improving the Quality of Students in Madrasah. *Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam Darussalam*, 7(1), 117–129. <https://doi.org/10.30739/JMPID.V7I1.3562>
- 13) Nyanyuki, N., Nyabwanga, R. N., & Nyamwamu, T. O. (2013). *An Assessment Of The Effect Of Accounting Practices On The Management Of Funds In Public Secondary Schools : A Study of Kisii Central District , Kenya*.
- 14) Pebrianto, D., Stie, D. A., & Balikpapan, M. (2022). Analisis Sistem Informasi Akuntansi Dalam Pengeluaran Kas Pada Penggunaan Dana Bantuan Operasional Sekolah (BOS) Reguler (Studi Kasus Pada Sd Al-Imam Islamic School Balikpapan) : *Madani Accounting And Management Journal*, 8(2), 42–53. <https://doi.org/10.51882/JAMM.V8I2.60>
- 15) Rahayu, S. D., & Lemmy, P. K. (2024). *Tantangan dan Strategi Pengelolaan Pembiayaan Pendidikan di Madrasah Swasta*. 3(2), 128–144.
- 16) Ristiyani, I., Solichatun, & Dimiyati, A. R. (2023). Dasar-Dasar Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Lembaga. In *Kemdikbudristek*.
- 17) Solehan. (2022). Manajemen Pembiayaan Pendidikan dalam Meningkatkan. *Edumaspul - Jurnal Pendidikan*, 6(1), 98–105. Retrieved from <https://publikasipips.ulm.ac.id/index.php/am/article/view/590>
- 18) Sugiyono. (2013). *Metodologi Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R & D* (19th ed.). Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 19) Veronika, E., & Asriati, N. (2024). Analisis Penerapan Akuntansi Pendidikan di SMP Amkur Bengkayang. *Journal of Mandalika Literature*, 5(4), 2745–5963. Retrieved from <https://sinta.kemdikbud.go.id/journals/profile/12219Aavailableonlineat:http://ojs.cahayamandalika.com/index.php/jml>
- 20) Zumarti, A., Amran, A., Mudasir, M., & Syarif, A. (2022). Manajemen Pembiayaan Sekolah dan Madrasah. *At-Tajdid : Journal of Islamic Studies*, 2(1), 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.24014/AT-TAJDID.V2I1.17888>